

Rice Ecosystems in Tanzania

Characterization and Classification

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Introduction

Rice is grown under very diverse ecosystems in the world. In Asian countries, rice ecosystems are distinctly defined and classified into irrigated, rainfed lowland, deep water, upland and tidal wetlands. Characterization and classification of rice ecosystems is inadequate in most rice growing countries in Africa, particularly in the Eastern, Central and Southern Africa (ECSA) region. The few available attempts to classify the ecosystems in Africa, are more generalized for either sub-regions (WARDA, 1980) or for the whole continent (Budenhagen, 1978).

In Tanzania, no attempts have been made to fully characterize and classify the existing rice ecosystems. Some rice research reports (Anon, 1990; 1991) have just mentioned the predominant rice ecosystems in the country. These too, have some controversial features.

This paper presents a description and possible classification of rice ecosystems in Tanzania. The description is largely based on source of water supply and management, land topography, soil moisture conditions and cultural practices. Quantitative distributions of respective ecosystems are also highlighted.

Major Ecosystems

In 1948, the East Africa Rice Commission categorized rice cultural systems in Tanzania into dryland, hilly and wetlands (lowland). Strictly, these can be grouped into two major ecosystems namely Lowland (wetland) and Upland (drylands) which can further be characterized into more detailed sub - ecosystems.

A. Lowland (Wetland) Ecosystem

Generally, this refers to the rice growing environments in which the rice fields are continuously flooded, except for occasional drainage. In Tanzania, rice fields under this ecosystem are accumulated with water during most of the growth duration. It is the most predominant rice growing environment covering about 80% of the total rice growing area. On the basis of water source supply and management together with cultural practices, lowland ecosystem in Tanzania can be subgrouped into

rainfed lowland and irrigated rice cultures (Fig. 1).

Rainfed Lowland Ecosystem

Water accumulating the rice fields is derived from rains. This can be direct from rainfall or river floods. The later is often due to heavy rains in mountains or highlands bordering river valley basins. This is typical in the valleys of rivers Kilombero, Rufiji, Wami, Ruvu and Pangani. It is also common in the swampy and floody northern shores of Lake Nyasa in Kyela basin.

In most of these areas, the rice growing environment is rainfed shallow flooded and submergence - prone. A few areas in this ecosystem can be characterized as shallow flooded - favourable with no serious drought and submergence problems.

Rainfed lowlands rice culture in Tanzania is also common in the swampy shores of Lake Victoria and Kalimawe plain in Same district and a number of scattered low-lying inland swamps of Bahi-Manyoni and Wembere in Nzega areas. The rice growing environments in Tabora and Shinyanga are grouped under this ecosystem. However, the rainfed lowland ecosystem in these areas is characterized as shallow-flooded and drought-prone. As a result rice crop experience frequent severe water deficit at any time of the growth stages.

Rainfed lowland ecosystem occupies about 74% of the total rice land in the country (Tanzania Mainland). In Zanzibar Islands, rainfed lowland rice culture covers 98% of the total rice production area of 1500 ha.

On the basis of water management and some cultural practices, rainfed lowlands ecosystem in Tanzania can be sub - categorized into the Bunded Shallow - Flooded and Unbunded Flooded rice growing environments.

Rainfed Lowland Unbunded and Flooded

Rice fields are not bunded except along the borders between adjacent farmer's fields where pulled weeds are heaped during weeding operations. This facilitates water accumulation in rice fields.

The ecosystem is more common than the shallow - Flooded and bunded rice culture in Morogoro, Mbeya, Mtwara, Tanga and Lindi regions. It is estimated to occupy about 42% of the total rice production area in the country (Fig. 1). In Zanzibar islands, 98% of total rice area (15,000 ha) is under the unbundled and not flooded but water - logged soil conditions.

In the mainland, the ecosystem is found in river valleys and floody valley basins of Kilombero, Ruvu, Wami, Rufiji, Pangani and Kyela Basin.

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Generally, areas where the ecosystem is common receive moderate to high average annual rainfall of about 800 – 1200 mm.

Under the unbunded shallow flooded rice culture, the crop is direct seeded by broadcasting or random dibbling when the soil is just moist enough for germination and seedling establishment. In early vegetative phase, the crop is growing only under water saturated conditions. Standing rain or floody water in fields start at mid tillering to early reproductive stage depending on the amount of rainfall and land topography of the area. Water depths vary, reaching 10 – 50 cm or more depending also on location and flood intensity. In some seasons, the uncontrolled rainwater in rice fields results in severe rice damage and yield losses due to submergence of the crop. The phenomenon is common in Kyela Basin, Kilombero–Rufiji floody plains and Mtwara river valleys.

Rainfed Bunded and Shallow Flooded

After ploughing, the fields are divided into small banded plots of 10m x 5m. This is common in Usangu Plains, Lake Rukwa and around Bahi and Wembere swampy plains. In Mwanza, Shinyanga and Tabora, the banded plots are permanent and larger than those mentioned above. Ploughing is done within the permanent plots. In both the small and large banded plots, puddling within the plots is mostly achieved by using hand hoe, when the plots are naturally flooded. A few farmers puddle their

plots using ox–ploughs.

Rice under this ecosystem is transplanted. Seedlings are normally raised in dry seed – beds for about 4 – 6 weeks.

This rainfed banded and shallow flooded ecosystem is common in areas with low to moderate average rainfall (i.e 500 – 700 mm). Bunding is therefore done to impound enough water needed by the crop during the growing season. It is also practiced in the swampy shores of Lake Victoria, in Mwanza, Shinyanga, Tabora and Usangu Plains in Mbeya. Other areas include the low – lying areas and swamps of Bahi and Wembere. The ecosystem occupies about 32% of the total rice production area in the country (Fig. 1).

Irrigated Rice Ecosystem

In Tanzania, irrigated rice culture can be characterized into two categories: Fully irrigated under large scale state farms and traditional supplementary irrigated rice under small farmers.

Fully Irrigated Rice

Large commercial rice farms are fully irrigated, highly mechanized and well managed. Rice is direct seeded in rows using seed drills. The fields are then subject to several intermittent flush irrigation for germination and seedling establishment before continuous flooding. The fully irrigated state owned commercial farms at Mbarali (6100 ha), Madibira (3000 ha), Kapunga (3800 ha), Dakawa (2000 ha)

Fig 1. Classification of Lowland Rice Ecosystem

and Ruvu (700 ha) occupy about 5% of the total rice area in the country. Yields at these farms, though vary with farm, are relatively high compared to any other rice ecosystems in Tanzania.

Small-holders Irrigated Rice Culture

Irrigated rice culture under small-holders are either fully irrigated or traditional and supplementary irrigation schemes scattered in Tabora, Morogoro, Mbeya, Dodoma, Kilimanjaro, Mara and Mtwara regions.

These small scale irrigated rice culture occupy about 1% of the total rice production area in the country (i.e 3800 ha). Under this ecosystem rice fields are permanently banded in small plots measuring about 20 m x 10 m. Ploughing is done within the small plots using ox-ploughs or hand-hoes. Puddling, is also done using hand hoes. Rice is transplanted in small plots using seedlings raised in dry seed beds for 4 – 6 weeks.

In peasant grown and irrigated rice, yields are higher than in the rainfed lowland growing environments. At Mombo Irrigation scheme, farmers have been able to produce up to 4.0 t/ha using one of the improved local Afaa Mwanza strains.

B. Upland Rice Ecosystem

This is a rice growing environment in which the crop is grown under rainfed naturally well drained soils and without standing water in the rice fields (Buddenhagen, 1978; Gupta 1983; IITA, 1984). The ecosystem is subdivided into the true (dryland) and the hydromorphic ecosystems. The ecosystem is sometimes dubbed as hilly rice.

This rice culture is common in Morogoro, Mbeya, Coast, Mtwara and Lindi regions. Rice under this ecosystem is found as patches in hilly and undulating land topography and mountain slopes. The ecosystem is also common in areas adjacent to the small lowland areas along stream courses. It is also found along the sandy coastal areas and islands of Zanzibar and Pemba. Upland rice culture occupies about 20% of the total rice area in Tanzania.

Dryland Ecosystem

Dryland upland ecosystem is common on slopes of Uluguru Mountains in Morogoro, Usambara and Ulanga-Kilombero mountain corridor. In Kyela Basin, dryland rice ecosystem is found in the hilly areas in the northern portion of the basin. Dryland rice ecosystem is common in whole of coastal strip. The estimated total area under this ecosystem is about 12%. Most of the dryland rice growing environments are unfavourably drought-prone due to frequent moisture stress. Soils are generally lighter and sandy with low water holding capacity. In some areas the soils are reddish to light brown and relatively less fertile.

Farmers in this ecosystem practice the slash-burn shifting cultivation system. Rice is direct seeded by random dibbling or broadcasting during the onset of long rains. Average yields under

this ecosystem are very low estimated between 0.4 to 0.5 t/ha.

Hydromorphic Ecosystem

In hydromorphic rice growing environments rice is grown on soils which are periodically saturated by fluctuating water table in addition to rainfall. It is also common – mistakenly grouped as rainfed lowland rice culture. However, in hydromorphic condition, the rice plants depend on both rain water and on underground water seepage.

In Tanzania, hydromorphic rice growing environments are in small scattered and narrow v-shaped depressions between hills or elevated areas in undulating land topography. Soils are relatively fertile compared to dryland rice lands. The ecosystem is commonly found in the Coast, Tanga, Morogoro, Lindi, Mtwara, Shinyanga and Mwanza. It occupies about 8% of the total rice area in the country.

Typical hydromorphic rice growing conditions are common along Dar es Salaam – Morogoro road around Kibaha – Bagamoyo areas. Rice is direct seeded by broadcasting or dibbling. Transplanting is used when filling the gaps.

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